
Numerical Analysis of A New Thermosyphon Heat Pipe

Çetin YAVUZ¹, Ali TAROKH², Aydın DİKİCİ³

¹Department of Electrical and Energy, Tatvan Vocational School, Bitlis Eren University, Bitlis, Turkey

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Lakehead University, Thunder Bay, Canada

³Department of Energy System Engineering, Firat University, Elazığ, Turkey

ABSTRACT

In this study, an experimental and 3-dimensional numerical analysis of a thermosyphon heat pipe (THP) using two-phase fluid cycling was performed to model the heat transfer process by evaporation and condensation. R404A refrigerant was chosen as the working fluid for the THP and 50% of the evaporator section was filled with the working fluid. Numerical analysis was performed using ANSYS FLUENT program and VOF method. In the meantime, in order to model the evaporation and condensation process successfully, a UDF code written in C was used and introduced to the fluent program. As a result of the study, it was seen that the temperature values obtained from the experimental and numerical analysis for the evaporator and condenser parts of the THP were in good agreement. As a result of the numerical analyzes carried out in 3D, the contours of the evaporation and condensation process and the heat transfer process are presented visually. The analysis took a total of 200 seconds.

Keywords: Thermosyphon heat pipe, Evaporation and condensation, ANSYS, VOF

1. INTRODUCTION

Heat pipes and/or thermosiphons are heat transfer devices that perform the fluid cycle in two phases in a vacuumed closed tube. A thermosyphon consists of 3 main parts, known as the evaporator, where the heat is given to the working fluid, adiabatic, and the condenser, where the condensation event is carried out. In the evaporator section, the working fluid is heated and evaporation is carried out. The resulting steam then reaches the adiabatic section and then the condenser section. Here, the steam coming into contact with the surface of the condenser section below the saturation temperature condenses and returns to the evaporator section again. This cycle continues throughout the operation of the THP [1]. THP's are used in many areas [2-7]. As a result of the literature research, it has been seen that many 2D numerical analyzes have been carried out for thermosiphons. However, there is no comprehensive 3D numerical analysis that reaches steady state. Therefore, this study is extremely important in this respect. As it is known, CFD analysis, which is used in the solutions and visualization of complex flow events occurring in the interior of thermosiphons, is effectively used in engineering fields due to its visualization possibilities and extremely efficient.

Kamburova et al. [8] carried out a numerical analysis in which they modeled the simultaneous evaporation and condensation event in a thermosyphon in 2D. They used the VOF technique and distilled water as the working fluid in their work. As a result of their studies, they reported that they successfully realized the complex flow events occurring in the thermosyphon. At the same time, they stated that it was in good agreement with the experimental results.

Yang et al. [9] carried out an experimental and numerical analysis of the thermal properties of a heat pipe. Researchers using UDF and VOF techniques in their studies stated that evaporation and condensation phenomena can be simulated with these methods. At the same time, they stated that the axial velocity fluctuation in most areas of the heat pipe was very small, and they reported that the velocity magnitudes changed from 0 to the maximum value from the end of the evaporator and condenser sections, and the maximum value was maintained in the adiabatic section.

Tarokh et al. [10] carried out a numerical analysis to improve the heat transfer performance of a thermosyphon with a vortex-forming barrier placed in its body. The researchers stated that the positioning of the barrier in the adiabatic and condenser sections had a very good effect on the overall thermal resistance and average wall temperature distribution.

Fadhl et al. investigated a thermosyphon heat pipe in two different studies. They used water, R134a and R404a as working fluid. The researchers, who evaluated the thermosyphon heat pipe using different heat inputs, stated that the average temperature values obtained from the numerical and experimental analyzes were in good agreement as a result of their studies. At the same time, they have successfully visualized the evaporation and condensation phenomenon using VOF and UDF techniques [11, 12].

Kim et al. [13] conducted a study examining the effects of mass transfer time relaxation parameters on a thermosyphon heat pipe. Using the mass transfer relaxation parameter as 0.1 for evaporation and 4 different values for condensation, they stated that the most appropriate β_c value was $0.1 \times (\rho_L/\rho_V)$. Using water as the working fluid,

researchers simulated evaporation and condensation using VOF and UDF techniques in their numerical analysis. Wang et al. [14] reported that the β_c value should be approximately 10-1000 times greater than the β_e value. This is also an indication that the mass transfer time relaxation parameters can be selected in accordance with the experimental results.

In this context, experimental and 3-dimensional numerical analyzes of a Thermosiphon heat pipe with a finned structure were carried out in the presented study. In the meantime, it is of great importance to choose the appropriate mass transfer time relaxation parameters for successful evaporation and condensation analysis. The mentioned values were determined as 0.1 for evaporation and 20 for condensation in this study. In addition, the numerical analyzes performed in this study were carried out using ANSYS FLUENT 2022R1 using high-performance computing (HPC) systems from the Digital Research Alliance of Canada.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

As mentioned before, complex flow events occurring inside the thermosiphon heat pipes are carried out by numerical analysis. However, the numerical analyzes in question are based on the finite volume method and the analyzes performed with two phases are much more difficult than those with single phase. Because the interfaces between the phases are movable in the analyzes carried out as two-phases. This situation brings with it a more intense computational effort [15, 16, 17]. As a result of the literature research, it has been seen that the VOF method is the most suitable method in terms of its convenience in monitoring the interface, and this method has been used in many studies in this field. With the VOF method, surface tracking of two or more fluids that do not mix with each other is carried out. Therefore, the VOF method was used in the numerical analysis in this study [15, 16, 17]. In this method, the volume fractions in both phases are added to the calculations and the sum of the volume fractions of both phases in any control volume is equal to one. This situation is expressed in the equation below.

$$\alpha_l + \alpha_v = 1 \tag{1}$$

If $\alpha_l=1$, the cell is completely filled with liquid.

If $\alpha_v=1$, the cell is completely filled with vapor.

If $0 < \alpha_l < 1$, both liquid phase and vapor phase are present in the cell [18].

At the same time, since the analysis performed in this study was performed in two phases, the continuity, momentum, and energy equations given below are expressed as vapor and liquid phases. The equations used for numerical analysis of the thermosiphon heat pipe are given below.

Continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_L \rho_L) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_L \rho_L \vec{u}) = S_M \tag{2}$$

The terms α_L , ρ_L , \vec{u} , t , and S_M in this equation represent the volume fraction for the liquid phase, density for the liquid phase, velocity, time, and the source term for mass, respectively.

Energy equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho e) + \nabla \cdot [\vec{u}(\rho e + \rho)] = \nabla \cdot (k \cdot \nabla T) + S_E \tag{3}$$

The terms T , ρ , \vec{u} , k , t , and S_E in the energy equation are the mass-averaged temperature shared by the phases, density, velocity, thermal conductivity, time, and source terms, respectively. The term e given in the equation represents the specific internal energy and is expressed by the equation below.

$$e = \frac{\rho_L \alpha_L e_L + \rho_V \alpha_V e_V}{\rho_L \alpha_L + \rho_V \alpha_V} \tag{4}$$

When Equation 4 is examined, it is seen that the terms e_L and e_V exist. These stand for the specific internal energy of the liquid and vapor phases, respectively, and these terms defined by the caloric equation of state [19] are expressed in equations 5 and 6.

$$e_L = C_{pL}(T - T_{sat}) \tag{5}$$

$$e_V = C_{pV}(T - T_{sat}) \tag{6}$$

Also, the terms ρ and k given in the energy equation are volume-averaged parameters and are expressed as follows.

$$\rho = \alpha_V \rho_V + (1 - \alpha_V) \rho_L \tag{7}$$

$$k = \alpha_V k_V + (1 - \alpha_V) k_L \tag{8}$$

Momentum equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \vec{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u} \vec{u}^T) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot [\mu(\nabla \vec{u} + \nabla \vec{u}^T)] + \rho \vec{g} + \vec{F}_{CSF} \quad (9)$$

The terms p , \vec{g} , μ , and \vec{F}_{CSF} in the momentum equation are local pressure, gravity, viscosity, and volumetric surface tension force, respectively. Here, the viscosity is volume-averaged and is expressed as follows. However, the volumetric surface tension force is expressed by equation 11 [20].

$$\mu = \alpha_V \mu_V + (1 - \alpha_V) \mu_L \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{F}_{CSF} = 2\sigma_{lv} \left(\frac{\alpha_L \rho_L C_V \nabla \alpha_V + \alpha_V \rho_V C_L \nabla \alpha_L}{\rho_V + \rho_L} \right) \quad (11)$$

The terms σ_{lv} , C_V , and C_L given in Equation 11 are surface tension and surface curvetures for vapor and liquid, respectively.

The expressions suggested by Lee and De schepper et al [21, 15] were used to calculate the mass and energy transfer in the numerical analysis of thermosiphon working in two phases. These expressions are given below:

For the mass transfer process;

Evaporation: $T_{mix} > T_{sat}$

$$S_M = -\beta_e \alpha_l \rho_l \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| \quad (12)$$

$$S_M = \beta_e \alpha_l \rho_l \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| \quad (13)$$

Condensation: $T_{mix} < T_{sat}$

$$S_M = \beta_c \alpha_v \rho_v \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| \quad (14)$$

$$S_M = -\beta_c \alpha_v \rho_v \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| \quad (15)$$

For the heat transfer process;

Evaporation: $T_{mix} > T_{sat}$

$$S_E = -\beta_e \alpha_l \rho_l \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| . LH \quad (16)$$

Condensation: $T_{mix} < T_{sat}$

$$S_E = \beta_c \alpha_v \rho_v \left| \frac{T_{mix} - T_{sat}}{T_{sat}} \right| . LH \quad (17)$$

The terms T_{mix} , T_{sat} , LH , β_e and β_c in the equations given for the mass and heat transfer process, the mixture temperature, saturation temperature, latent heat, the mass transfer time relaxation parameters for evaporation and condensation, respectively. As mentioned before, these values should be chosen in accordance with the experimental results in order to perform the evaporation and condensation analyzes successfully and to match the experimental and numerical results. In this study, β_e and β_c parameters were determined as 0.1 and 20, respectively. At the same time, the equations given above for mass and heat transfer were written in UDF using the C programming language and introduced to the fluent program.

Mesh and boundary conditions applied in numerical analysis

The thermosyphon heat pipe presented in this study has an outer diameter of 25 mm and a total length of 700 mm. The material from which THP is produced is aluminum. The lengths of the evaporator, adiabatic and condenser sections are 120, 270 and 310 mm, respectively, and are shown in Fig. 1a. The thermosiphon heat pipe consists of 3556874 nodes and 3430000 elements, and the mesh structure in question is indicated in Fig. 1b. The boundary condition for the inner walls of the thermosiphon heat pipe is chosen as no-slip. The gravitational acceleration is taken as -9.81 m/s². A constant temperature boundary condition has been applied for the evaporator and condenser section, and these temperature values are 323.15 and 283.15 K, respectively. The zero-flux boundary condition was chosen for the adiabatic section. The operating pressure value was determined as 1084400 Pascal in accordance with the saturation temperature taken as 293.15 K. The initialization process was carried out at the saturation temperature after the patch process was performed in such a way that 50% of the evaporator section was the working fluid and the remaining section was steam. The working fluid was used as R404A. The analysis was carried out at 20 C saturation temperature and the properties of the fluid were determined in accordance with this temperature value and given in Table 1.

a- THP Sections b- Mesh
Figure 1. THP sections and mesh structure

Table 1. Properties of working fluid

Properties	Primary phase	Secondary phase
ρ [kg/m ³]	56.306	1067.3
μ [kg/m.s]	0.011849	0.00013748
k [W/m.K]	0.015178	0.065499
σ_{lv} [11]	$\sigma_{lv} = 0.09805856 - 1.845 \times 10^{-5}T - 2.3 \times 10^{-7}T^2$ (18)	
C_p [J/kg.K]	1163.6	1502
LH [kJ/kg]	374.74	228.75

The time step size used in the numerical analysis was chosen as 0.0005 and thus the courant number remained below 2 throughout the analysis. The SIMPLE algorithm has been chosen for pressure-velocity coupling. First-order upwind discretization, Geo-Reconstruct and Presto discretization were chosen for momentum and energy equations, volume fraction and pressure interpolation, respectively. Explicit formulation was used in the numerical analysis performed within the scope of the study. Residuals are determined as 10^{-4} for volume fraction and velocity, and 10^{-6} for energy. The saturation temperature and enthalpy value of the working fluid are specified in the UDF code.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical analyzes carried out within the scope of this study took a total of 200 seconds. The said numerical analysis became steady state after 200 seconds. As a result of the constant temperature boundary condition applied to the walls of the evaporator section, the working fluid in this section is heated and nucleate boiling occurs. The steam that emerges later reaches the adiabatic and then the condenser section over time. The steam, which comes into contact with the walls of the condenser section below the saturation temperature, condenses here and reaches the evaporator section again. This process was continued until the system reached the steady state and at the end of 200 seconds, when the system reached the steady state, the analysis was completed. Images of the above-mentioned process are given later in this section.

The average temperature values obtained from the experimental and numerical results of the evaporator and condenser section are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Average temperature values obtained from experiment and numerical analysis and Relative error

Section	$T_{EXP,ave}$ (K)	$T_{CFD,ave}$ (K)	$Re(\%)$
Evaporator	320.97003	313.3941618	2,36
Condenser	297.4961	299.16323895	0.56

When the table above is examined, it is seen that the average temperature values obtained from the experimental and numerical analyzes are in perfect harmony with each other. Especially when the relative error values are looked at, it can be clearly seen that the condenser and evaporator sections fit very well.

Fig. 2 shows the contours of the evaporation and condensation event occurring in the THP. When these contours are examined, it can be seen that the pool boiling event occurs in the form of nucleate boiling and the condensation takes place in the first times when the analysis starts. As a result of heating the evaporator section, the temperature value of the working fluid increased over time and evaporation started with the formation of bubbles at the points where it reached the boiling point. These bubbles that emerged later moved upwards in the pool and came to the upper part of the pool. Here, the steam in the bubbles reached the upper part and was released and started to rise towards the condenser part with the effect of the pressure difference. Here, the vapor condensed in the form of droplets came back to the evaporator section with the effect of gravity. As a result of this event, which took place during the numerical analysis process, after a small decrease in the amount of liquid occurred, it remained stable after 200 seconds, and thus the system reached a stable structure.

Figure 2. Evaporation and condensation contours of THP in 0.1-0.2-5-15-50-100-150 and 200 seconds, respectively

Fig. 3 shows the temperature contours that occur inside the THP. Between 0.1 and 15th seconds, the temperature increased in seconds and after 15th seconds, the average temperature value of THP no longer changed and became uniform. When Fig. 3 is examined, it can be easily seen that the temperature of the THP no longer changes after 15th seconds.

Figure 3. Temperature contours of THP in 0.1-5-15-50-100-150 and 200 seconds, respectively

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, an experimental and 3D numerical analysis of a thermosiphon was carried out. The average temperature values obtained from the experiments for the condenser and evaporator sections were compared with the values obtained from the CFD analysis. It has been seen that the results are in very good agreement. especially the average temperature values of the condenser section were found to be very close to the experimentally obtained values. As a result of the CFD analysis performed, the evaporation and condensation event was successfully modeled and visualized.

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